

Reactions of 2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine with some Acids and Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Salts

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2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine (bBzlH₂Py) reacts with aqueous hydrohalic and perchloric acids to give adducts of the type bBzlH₂Py.HX (X=Cl, Br, I or ClO₄). The *N*-heterocycle also reacts with the salts of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) to yield complexes of the types MX₂(bBzlH₂Py) (M=Co; X=Cl, Br or I; and M=Ni; X=Cl or Br) and MX₂(bBzlH₂Py)₂.nH₂O (M=Co; X=Cl, Br or I; n=2; and M=Ni; X=Cl, Br or I; n=1; X=ClO₄; n=0). Ir and electronic spectral studies and magnetic susceptibility measurements, suggest that the monoheterocycle complexes possess a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry, whereas the biheterocycle complexes have a square-pyramidal (for cobalt) or octahedral (for nickel) structures.

TRANSITION metal complexes containing *N*-heterocycles have attracted considerable attention in recent years in view of their possible catalytic activity¹ and biological importance². Several related complexes, a majority of which containing either monodentate and/or bidentate *N*-heterocycles, have been reported earlier from this laboratory³⁻⁷. The studies have now been extended to investigate the reactivity of a multidentate *N*-heterocycle, 2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine (**1**; bBzlH₂Py)⁸⁻¹⁰ towards some acids and salts of cobalt and nickel. Nelson and coworkers¹¹ briefly reported the characterisation of an octahedral cationic complex, [Ni(bBzlH₂Py)₂]²⁺ (as ClO₄⁻ or BPh₄⁻ salt).

1

Experimental

2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine was prepared according to the literature method⁸. Hydrated cobalt(II) chloride and nickel(II) halides were from B.D.H. Cobalt(II) bromide, cobalt(II) iodide, cobalt(II) perchlorate, nickel(II) iodide and nickel(II) perchlorate were prepared by dissolving the corresponding carbonates in 1:1 aqueous hydrobromic, hydroiodic and perchloric acids respectively, and evaporating the resulting solutions to almost dryness under reduced pressure. The infrared (nujol) and solid state (nujol) as well as solution electronic spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss SPECORD 75 IR and a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometers respectively. Magnetic moments were measured with a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as the calibrant. Conductivity measurements were made with a Toshniwal CL 01.02 conductivity bridge.

2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine hydrohalic/perchloric acid salts, bBzlH₂Py.HX (X=Cl, Br, I, ClO₄): To a solution of bBzlH₂Py in ethanol the corresponding acid in excess was added and the resultant solution was refluxed on a steam-bath for 0.5 h. A cream solid got separated instantaneously was washed with water and dried under reduced pressure.

Dihalo mono(2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine)cobalt(II) complexes, CoX₂(bBzlH₂Py) (X=Cl, Br, I): A solution of cobalt(II) halide (1 mmol) and the *N*-heterocycle (1 mmol) in ethanol (15–20 ml) (THF or acetone in the case of bromo or iodo complex) was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting green solid was washed with ethanol or THF or acetone and dried under reduced pressure.

Dihalo bis(2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine)cobalt(II) complexes, CoX₂(bBzlH₂Py)₂.2H₂O (X=Cl, Br, I): To an alcoholic or acetone (10 ml) solution of cobalt(II) halide (1 mmol), the *N*-heterocycle (2 mmol) in ethanol or acetone (10 ml) was added and the mixture refluxed for about 3 h. The resulting yellow solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Dihalo mono(2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine)nickel(II) complexes, NiX₂(bBzlH₂Py) (X=Cl, Br, I): A solution of nickel(II) halide (1 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was dehydrated by the addition of triethylorthoformate (ca. 5 ml) at refluxing temperature for 10 min. To it was added the *N*-heterocycle (1 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) and the refluxing continued for 2 h. The resulting greenish yellow solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Dihalo bis(2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine)nickel(II) complexes, NiX₂(bBzlH₂Py)₂.H₂O (X=Cl, Br, I): To a solution of nickel(II) halide (1 mmol) dissolved in isopropanol–ethanol (5:10 ml) mixture, the *N*-heterocycle (2 mmol) in isopropanol (10 ml) was added. Immediately a straw coloured compound got separated and the mixture was digested

for 1 h on a steam-bath. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Bis(2,6-bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine)metal(II) perchlorate complexes, $M(bBzIH_2Py)_2(ClO_4)_2$ ($M=Co, Ni$): The complexes were prepared in the same way as the corresponding halo compounds.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of $bBzIH_2Py$ with some acids: 2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine reacts with aqueous hydrohalic or perchloric acids (in excess) in ethanol to form cream coloured solids corresponding to the composition $bBzIH_2Py.HX$ ($X=Cl, Br, I$ or ClO_4). The acid adducts are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but dissolve in dimethylformamide in which they are weakly conducting (Table 1).

The infrared spectrum of the heterocycle shows a broad peak around 3120 cm^{-1} assignable to the stretching frequency of hydrogen bonded N-H moiety. A set of three bands at 1600, 1590 and 1570 cm^{-1} may be assigned to coupled C=N and C=C stretching vibrations^{1,2}. The ν_{C-N} and δ_{NH} vibrations are probably very close to one another and occur at 1315 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the acid adducts are comparable with that of $bBzIH_2Py$, and the perchlorate adduct shows additional bands particularly around 1100 cm^{-1} which arise due to weak coordination of ClO_4^- via oxygen(s)^{1,3} to proton(s) of the imino nitrogens.

The solid state electronic spectra of the heterocycle and the acid adducts are not well-resolved to locate any bands. However, their solution spectra in DMF show three prominent bands around 29 000, 30 000 and $32\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which arise due to the pyridine unit of the heterocycle^{1,4}.

Reactions of $bBzIH_2Py$ with cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts: 2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)pyridine reacts with the halides of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) in the mole ratio of 2:1 in ethanol (acetone/i-propanol in the case of iodides) to give yellow or straw coloured compounds of the composition $MX_n(bBzIH_2Py)_2.nH_2O$ ($X=Cl, Br$ or I ; $M=Co$; $n=2$; $M=Ni$; $n=1$). Under similar conditions, if the ligand-to-metal stoichiometry is 1:1, greenish to yellow coloured complexes of the formula $MX_2(bBzIH_2Py)$ ($M=Co$; $X=Cl, Br$ or I ; $M=Ni$; $X=Cl$ or Br) are obtained, excepting the iodo complex of nickel(II). In the latter case, addition of the heterocycle to a solution of nickel(II) iodide instantaneously yields red crystals (1:1 complex), which gradually change to green (2:1 complex); presumably the 1:1 complex formed is too unstable for isolation. The complexes are sparingly soluble in common organic solvents but freely dissolve in DMF in which some of them appear to decompose as evidenced by colour changes and conductivity data. However, $CoX_2(bBzIH_2Py)_2$ complexes behave as 1:1 electrolytes in ethanol^{1,5} (Table 1).

The nitrogen heterocycle also reacts with the perchlorates of cobalt and nickel in various ligand-

metal stoichiometries to produce complexes of the type $M(bBzIH_2Py)_2(ClO_4)_2$ ($M=Co, Ni$) only. Interestingly, the perchlorate complex of cobalt behaves as a uni-univalent electrolyte in acetonitrile, whereas the nickel analog is a uni-bivalent electrolyte^{1,6}.

The aforesaid complexes are paramagnetic and the solid state magnetic moment values are in the range 4.10–4.60 B.M. for the cobalt complexes and 2.70–3.10 B.M. for the corresponding nickel complexes (Table 1).

The infrared spectral features of the halo complexes are almost similar to those of the uncoordinated heterocycle except for minor shifts in the positions of the bands. The ν_{NH} band at 3140 cm^{-1} of the heterocycle is present in the metal complexes suggesting that the heterocycle is coordinated to the metal ion via the pyridine nitrogen(s) rather than the imino nitrogen(s). In the case of the perchlorate complexes of cobalt and nickel additional bands around 1100 and 620 cm^{-1} due to perchlorate groups are observed and the spectral features are characteristic of the presence of at least one of the perchlorates coordinated to the metal in the former complex^{1,3}. This observation is also supported by the conductivity data.

The solid state electronic spectra of $CoX_2(bBzIH_2Py)$ ($X=Cl$ or Br) complexes show three prominent bands around 15 500, 17 800 and $20\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In DMF solution these bands undergo shift to longer wavelength regions. The spectral features and the positions of the bands are comparable with those having a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry^{1,6}. In view of this, the above complexes may be suggested to have a trigonal bipyramidal geometry, in which case the heterocycle would function as a chelating tridentate ligand coordinating via the three pyridine nitrogen atoms to the metal. The above electronic spectral bands may be respectively assigned to ${}^4A'_2 \rightarrow {}^4E'(F)$, ${}^4A'_2 \rightarrow {}^4A'_2(P)$ and ${}^4A'_2 \rightarrow {}^4E''(P)$ transitions^{1,7,18}. For the iodo complex, the solid state visible absorption bands occur around 13 000, 17 000 and $21\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The complex appears to decompose in DMF as indicated by its electronic spectrum.

The solid state electronic spectra of $CoX_2(bBzIH_2Py)_2.2H_2O$ ($X=Cl, Br$ or I) and $[Co(bBzIH_2Py)_2(OCIO_3)]ClO_4$ show very weak bands in the visible region at 11 500–13 000, 16 500 and $20\,000\text{--}22\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2) which are ascribed to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4B_2(F)$, ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4E(P)$ and ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_2(P)$ transitions respectively^{1,9}. The positions of the bands suggest a square-pyramidal structure for the complexes. The electronic spectra of the complexes have also been recorded in DMF solution. The chloro complex which is yellow in colour changes to green, whereas the bromo, iodo and perchlorato complexes retain their yellow colour in DMF.

The solid state electronic spectra of $NiX_2(bBzIH_2Py)$ ($X=Cl$ or Br) complexes display weak bands in the visible region around 11 500, 12 400

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p./ Decp. °C	Λ^* $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
bBz1H ₂ Py.H ₂ O	White	358	—	—	68.95 (69.29)	4.65 (4.59)	21.17 (21.25)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HCl	Cream	349	12 ^a	—	66.08 (65.61)	4.19 (4.06)	19.71 (20.14)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HBr	Cream	331	18 ^a	—	58.17 (58.17)	4.93 (3.60)	19.40 (17.86)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HI	Cream	278	72 ^a	—	49.28 (51.95)	3.65 (3.21)	15.34 (15.94)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HClO ₄	Cream	359	38 ^a	—	55.78 (55.56)	3.78 (3.20)	17.07 (17.04)
CoCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	Green	>350	39 ^a	4.65	52.20 (51.72)	2.99 (2.97)	16.48 (15.87)
CoBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	Green	>350	49 ^a	4.61	42.30 (43.04)	2.68 (2.47)	12.40 (12.20)
CoI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	Greenish brown	>250	128 ^a	4.59	35.88 (35.88)	2.07 (2.10)	11.14 (11.22)
CoCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	>350	47 ^b	4.20	57.47 (57.89)	3.58 (3.84)	17.67 (17.77)
CoBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	>350	53 ^b	4.18	51.84 (52.01)	3.04 (3.45)	15.90 (15.97)
CoI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	235	58 ^b	4.29	46.17 (46.98)	2.74 (3.11)	13.92 (14.42)
[Co(bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	Yellow	>350	143 ^a	4.45	52.07 (51.84)	2.91 (2.98)	15.83 (15.90)
NiCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	Greenish yellow	>250	58 ^a	2.96	51.76 (51.76)	2.97 (3.15)	15.88 (15.53)
NiBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	Greenish yellow	>250	104 ^a	2.87	42.25 (43.07)	3.07 (2.47)	12.43 (13.21)
NiCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	Straw	>250	53 ^a	2.86	59.53 (59.26)	3.53 (3.66)	18.25 (18.18)
NiBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	Straw	>250	86 ^a	2.71	52.72 (53.12)	3.20 (3.29)	16.01 (16.30)
NiI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	Straw	200	124 ^a	2.99	48.80 (47.88)	2.80 (2.96)	14.97 (14.59)
[Ni(bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	Straw	>250	131 ^a	2.86	51.87 (51.84)	3.04 (3.00)	15.78 (15.91)

*Molar conductance of $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions in ^aDMF, ^bethanol, ^cacetonitrile.TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES^a

Compd.	λ_{max} in nujol $\times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$	λ_{max} in DMF ($\epsilon, \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) $\times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
bBz1H ₂ Py	—	29.2(15.0), 30.2(16.8), 31.7(14.8)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HCl	—	29.2(19.7), 30.2(22.1), 31.7(19.5)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HBr	—	29.2(16.9), 30.2(19.0), 31.6(16.8)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HI	—	29.2(37.3), 30.3(42.8), 31.8(37.8)
bBz1H ₂ Py.HClO ₄	—	29.3(16.2), 30.2(17.8), 31.6(15.8)
CoCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	13.4, 15.9, 17.8, 20.3	14.8(0.20), 16.4(0.1), 27.7(20.5), 29.7(24.1), 31.7(22.8)
CoBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	15.8, 17.5, 20.5	12.9(0.02), 14.7(0.04), 15.6(0.04), 16.2(0.03), 20.1(0.10), 30.1(30.7), 34.5(32.1)
CoI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	12.9, 17.2, 18.9, 20.5	20.6(0.03), 24.1(16.8), 27.7(36.6), 30.0(100.5), 34.1(65.6)
CoCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	13.4, 16.0, 23.4	14.8(0.07), 16.5(0.05), 26.8(23.7), 30.1(55.9), 31.9(51.7), 33.7(39.3)
CoBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	13.4, 17.1, 20.7	26.8(16.9), 30.2(54.4), 31.7(50.6), 34.0(36.6)
CoI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .2H ₂ O	11.5, 17.3, 20.4	20.6(0.26), 23.7(6.5), 27.7(36.6), 30.0(100.5), 31.7(36.0)
[Co(bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	11.6, 17.1, 22.3	26.7(26.6), 29.8(54.8), 31.7(43.4), 33.9(31.5)
NiCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	11.6, 12.5, 14.3	11.5(0.01), 12.9(0.01), 14.7(0.01), 27.7(9.9), 31.4(12.6)
NiBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py)	11.6, 12.4, 14.7	11.6(0.01), 12.7(0.01), 14.8(0.01), 27.2(6.5), 31.4(12.5)
NiCl ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	11.9, 17.7, 25.2	12.1(0.02), 18.2(0.02), 25.2(2.2), 27.8(30.9), 31.1(103.0)
NiBr ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	11.8, 17.7, 25.2	11.7(0.02), 17.8(0.01), 25.0(1.2), 27.3(40.0), 30.4(51.4)
NiI ₂ (bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂ .H ₂ O	11.8, 17.9, 25.0	11.6(0.04), 17.7(0.01), 25.0(1.3), 27.2(5.1), 30.5(6.6)
[Ni(bBz1H ₂ Py) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	12.0, 18.2, 24.9	11.7(0.05), 17.8(0.03), 25.0(1.1), 27.3(166.4), 30.9(209.2)

and $14\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The spectral features are comparable with those of the five-coordinate complexes of the type $[\text{Ni}(\text{Me}_6\text{tren})\text{X}]\text{X}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NCS}$) which are suggested to have a trigonal bipyramidal geometry²⁰. Further, the solution (in DMF) spectral features of the complexes are comparable with those observed in the solid state.

The electronic spectra (nujol) of the complexes $\text{NiX}_2(\text{bBzI}H_2\text{Py})_2 \cdot H_2O$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I) and $[\text{Ni}(\text{bBzI}H_2\text{Py})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ show bands around $12\,000$, $18\,000$ and $25\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The positions and low intensities of the bands suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes²¹. Similar spectral features are also observed in the spectra of the complexes taken in DMF. The results suggest that the octahedral stereochemistry continues to exist in solution.

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